

OSUN STATE YOUTH EMPOWERMENT SCHEME: A KEY TO SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.

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ABSTRACT.

Wide-spread poverty and insecurity emanated from gross unemployment of youths seemed threatening the realisation of individual and societal socio-economic progress as well as the nation's sustainable development and nascent democracy. Youths in their numerical, energy, and creative strength are the most reliable change agents. Unemployment in any form globally propels youth restlessness, crime and associated vices and the attendant threats to nation building, peace and security. In a bid to tackle unemployment and other fundamental problems, the State Government of Osun under the visionary leadership of Mr. Rauf Adesoji Aregbesola embarked on six action-packed people programmes that guarantee development with citizens' participation in the Education, Rural and Urban Renewal, Infrastructural Development, Agriculture, Health, Entrepreneurship and Job creation christened Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme (OYES) to fast track development and banish hunger and poverty. This paper examined the challenges and prospects of OYES vis-à-vis its implications in the development of the State. Structured questionnaires were administered to gather relevant information from total sample of 120 OYES cadet members in three local government areas in the State. Data collected were analyzed using correlation analysis. The results of the study showed: that there is significant relationship between youth empowerment and State development; that the general objectives of OYES are achievable. On the basis of the results of the study, the researcher recommended that one, governments' empowerment programmes should be encouraged, centered on participatory approach. Two, government should reach out to more youths, regardless of their ethnic, cultural, religious, educational background and geographical or political affiliation, and three, that the programme should be legislated so that new/succeeding government would not obstruct its continuity for sustainable development.

KEYWORDS: Empowerment, Youth, Development, Sustainable, Unemployment, OYES.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria as well as many other countries in the world is facing the worst burden of youth unemployment. Many Nigerians youths roam the streets in rural and urban centres without gainful job and the danger of this situation has far reaching implications on the social wellbeing and security of the country because the idle mind is the devil's workshop. *"The implications of youth unemployment are of social, economic, political. It can be argued that youth unemployment is potentially dangerous as it portends disturbing signals to all segments of the society. The rate of youth unemployment is high in the state of Osun, and it seems to have remained so even during the economic boom while its problems could be traced to many well-known factors among which are: Non-availability of jobs both in the private and public sector of the economy, lack of required skills among job seekers and absence of loan facility to those who deserve it for self-employment among others (Ogbonnaya, 2010)."*

Ujah and Komolafe (2012) stipulated that "economic growth drop to 7.6% in 2011, unemployment rose to 23%". Those who suffer most from this problem are millions of youths who resorted to criminal means for survival through cybercrime, armed robbery, prostitution, militancy, kidnapping, political thugs, etcetera.

The Bureau of Statistics according to Osun Defender (2012) reported that the overall national unemployment rate has been on the steady increase since 2005. For instance, it increased from 11.9% in 2005 to 21.1% in September, 2011 while unemployment rate in the State of Osun had double from 6.30% in 2007 to 12.6% in March, 2009. The determination to arrest the ugly trends necessitated the current effort by the Governor of State of Osun, Ogbeni Rauf Adesoji Aregbesola to not only empower 20,000 youths in Community Development Programmes (CDP) but also embarked on developmental projects aimed at taking the State and citizenry out of poverty to socio-economic prosperity. Past government administrations instituted State Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (SEEDS) in the State of Osun even

before the administration of the incumbent governor, yet unemployment was still on high side. This study therefore investigated the phenomenon and provided possible solutions.

Objective of the Study

The purpose of this research work is to:

- Discuss the challenges, prospects of Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme (OYES) and deployment of volunteer youths in various segments of the programmes.
- Clarify youth empowerment as means of facilitating development in the State of Osun.

Literature Review

Youth empowerment is a process whereby young people gain the ability and authority to make decisions and implement change in their own lives. It ranges from economic empowerment to social ideological, educational, technological and political empowerment (Omotere, 2011). In Nigeria, youth empowerment occurs in homes, at schools, through Youth Organisations, Government programmes, reality TV shows, orientations and seminars, and Community Organising Campaigns. The term ‘youth empowerment’ combines two important words (“youth” and “empowerment”) which must be defined differently. Youths are individual persons between the ages of 18-30 years. It is a means of encouraging young people to gain the practical skills, knowledge and exposure that will allow them to face and address overcome obstacles in life. The Leadership (2012) submitted: “Although Nigeria is often referred to as the richest country in West Africa, unemployment has been a major problem in the country since 1980, when the nation’s economy took a nosedive. The menace has been described as a time bomb that might explode anytime if no serious attention is paid in engaging the growing army of unemployed youths that have taken over the streets of the nation.”

Youth empowerment is the outcome by which youths, as change agents, gain the skills that impact their own lives within and outside host communities. Omotere (2011) noted that ‘youth empowerment at the individual level is exercising power over one’s life by being skilled, critically aware, and active in creating community change. Youth empowerment at the organisation level is the implication of culture, vision, and system that support youth empowerment at individual level. Skill development: This is the process of strengthening the skills of youth so that they know how to effectively make decisions positively and interact with their peers. Critical awareness: This is the process of providing youths with the information and resources necessary for analyzing issues that affect their lives and environments as well as strategize on ways to act as change agent. Opportunity: This is the process of providing youth the platforms for decision making and engaging them in community development/change.

The Concept of Osun Youth Empowerment

The inauguration of OYES was a demonstration of one of Governor Rauf Aregbesola’s campaign promises to make the State of Osun an industrial haven in which youths as leaders of tomorrow would be catered for in the area of skills acquisition, poverty alleviation, job and wealth creation. Fulfilling his promise to create 20,000 jobs within 100 days in office as governor, OYES a palliative livelihood for 20000 out of 250000 unemployment youth applicants, mainly graduates, was launched by the State Government in the year 2011 under the administration of Governor, Ogbeni Rauf Adesoji Aregbesola as a planned action aimed at tackling the problems of unemployment and physical development in the Virtuous State (State of Omoluabi) in order to rescue the State of Osun from poor governance and install progressive governance. The State did not only target the youths who are seen as engines of economic and social development but also primary school children who are enjoying free feeding (O-Meal) and the aged people (Agba Osun) for free Medicare and N10000 monthly stipend .

Youth empowerment can be defined as the process whereby the creative potentials of the young people between the ages of 18 and 30 years old are developed to gain the ability and authority to make decisions and implement pragmatic changes affecting their lives. Therefore it was joyous and memorable when on the 26th of November 2010 the Ibadan Division of the Court of Appeal adjudged Mr Rauf Adesoji Aregbesola the duly elected Governor of Osun State in the Gubernatorial and House of Assembly elections held on April 14, 2007.

OYES objectives.

Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme is a voluntary and interventionist community services organisation (CSO) with the following aims. (i) To help channel the lateral potential young people into productive social and economic activity, whilst at the same time being mindful of their current livelihood conditions and capabilities. (ii) To restore sense of community, individual, self-esteem and worth to our youth, 20000 of who were selected impartially as pioneer members. (iii) To create a moral and ethical overhaul by remolding the value of our youths towards making them pursue honour and integrity/virtuousness and (iv) To give the candidates entrepreneurship opportunities through new skills training.

Systematic empowerment

Having identified the implications of youth unemployment and the importance of youths on the state development, the State Government of Osun had systematically empowered the youths and adults of Osun through saleable/practicable skills acquisition embedded in OYES schemes to address youth unemployment in the State for future developmental purposes using the following modalities:

Attitudes Re-Orientate Training: - This meant to expose the youth to leadership skill, discipline and imbibe them with the virtue spirit that will make them free from any misdemeanor in discharging of their duties.

OYES-tech- Information technology (IT) has become phenomena in the world today and which had created much opportunities for the jobless in Nigeria is that of technology. Hence the OYES officials decided to educate cadet members with computer technology training ranging from computer repair, dismantling and assembling of GSM-handsets and related devices, training of computer packages such as Corel draw, micro soft office, power point, page maker and many more. The Corp members also choose the time convenient for them in the tutorial.

O-poultry- The state of Osun well imbued the Corp members into poultry farming such as catfish rearing in the State so that the Corp members will be self-reliant after their graduation instead of seeking white collar jobs endlessly without success.

O-beef/O-ram programme is designed for the Corp members to exploit cattle rearing business because of the economic advantages that pervaded the business and for economic sustenance.

O-reap. This is also designed for rural enterprise and agriculture programme. The cadet members were trained in the agro-allied production ranging from animals husbandry, fishery, yams; cassava and cocoa plantations, maize, beans, vegetables, etcetera as well as the processing of agricultural product into semi-finished or finished goods for both industrial customers and private consumers usage.

O-meal- This is another people's programme by the State government of Osun to feed the public primary schools pupils in the state free of charge. OYES cadets would be major suppliers of raw food items from their agro-allied businesses.

O-power- This acquisition of skill is for the Corp members deployed to learn the process of generating electric power supply in the State. It will enable the trainees to study and create alternative (Bio-Gas) to the epileptic power supply that pervaded the state.

O-tour- Is a deployment of OYES Corp members into the tourism centres so as to be creative in nature and try as much as possible to promote tourism orientation and make Osun a most tourism centre like that of Dubai.

O-clean Plus (Sanitation Czars). This is for environmental sanitation of the State to promote all-round cleanliness, good health of the people because health is wealth, and also to attract foreign investors.

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Green Gang- Some of the corps was also deployed to the green gang for State security purpose both at the daytime and night for the protection of citizenry and government installations.

Traffic Marshall- likewise some of the OYES Corp members were deployed to Traffic control system in the state of Osun because of the over conjunction of the Traffic law abiding with the assessment of vehicle document for road worthy.

Public Work- the state of Osun deployed some of the OYES cadets to the public works such as road repair and maintenance

Paramedics. For good health and cleanness in case of accident, hospitalization; some of the youth corps were also trained and deployed into this segment to deal with cases on citizen health.

Teacher corps. Some of the cadets having teaching qualifications were deployed to the teachers' corps segment so as to train and educate pupils and students at different level of primary and secondary schools to give them sound educational background.

Sheriff corps is equivalent to the Federal Government Road Safety Corpsto address issues on high roads. The cadetsare also involved in educating the motorist to be conscious when driving and be traffic law abiding.

OYES is economic empowerment, par excellence, which reduces social inequalities, improves standard of living as well making the youths better-off and reduced crimes that are often associated with idle hands.

Youths in the development of State

Sustainable development, according to Oyeshola (2008), *“describes a process in which the natural resources base is not allowed to deteriorate. It emphasizes the hitherto unappreciated role of the environmental quality and environmental inputs in the process of raising real income and quality of life. It is a new way of life and approach to social and economic activities for all societies, rich and poor which is compatible with the preservation of the environment.”*

Youths occupied a prominent place in any developing or developed nation. “Apart from being the owners and leaders of tomorrow, they outnumber the middle-age. Besides numerical superiority, youth have energy and ideas that are State potentials (Anasi, 2010). Federal Government of Nigeria (2001) on National Youth Development Policy asserted that: *“Youths are the foundation of a society; their energies, inventiveness, character and orientation defines the pace of development and security of a nation. Through their creative talents and labour power, a nation makes giant strides in economic development and socio-political attainments. In their dreams and hopes, a nation founds her motivation; on their energies, she builds her vitality and purpose, and because of their dreams and aspirations, the future of a nation or state is assured”*

The above statement acknowledges the role of youth in the peace, security and building of a nation. As the most active segment of any society, youths are the determiners of peace and stability of a nation. Conversely, the degree of disorderliness and instability in society is also determined on the part of youth. Peace is a precursor of development. The absence of peace means that no meaningful development can take place. The National Youth Policy (2001) affirms that the extent of the youth's responsible conduct and roles in society is positively correlated with the development of their country.

Youth empowerment and national development

National-building is associated with national integration, national consciousness, national unity, construction and modification of socio-political and economic structures so as to move with the global trends.

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It is concerned with the overall development of a nation socially, economically and politically. This view is corroborated by Ona (2012) who submitted that "nation-building is a multi-faceted, complex process of building the socio-political and economic dynamics of a political society in such a way as to facilitate the policy's continued independence sustenance, development and growth. As a vibrant group, the educated and empowered youths can easily be mobilized positively. They can form formidable pressure groups to press home desirable changes in the political leadership at any tier of the government. They can use their energy, determination and enlightened position to disseminate information to others so as to create political awareness and consciousness against evil and selfish political machination. If youths are empowered, one can predict with some degree of certainty a more transformed Nigerian nation, most probably devoid of corruption, nepotism, political manipulation which has for long characterized Nigeria's political landscape."

Youth employment in agriculture not only ensures food sufficiency but also reduces unemployment rate, idleness and poverty. Ifaturoti(2012) observed that unemployment compounds the problems the youths are facing in Nigeria; by being idle, they are prone to such vices as prostitution, armed robbery and rape."

Prospects of OYES Scheme

OYES was inaugurated purposely for the development of the state of Osun which cannot be achieved in a day but through a gradual process which could take a couple of years to be achieved. Ifaturoti (2012) recounted the prospects of Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme as follows: "Full infrastructural maturity of the on-going vocational training programmes for the cadets. Partnerships with banks for the provision of credit facilities so that the cadets can engage 'gainfully' in small scale businesses and activities. Access to donor or development funds and increased global recognition. Creation of substantial volume of permanent employment for the pioneer OYES cadets. The development programme is targeting to bring 500,000 youths of the State of Osun into the scheme to boost employment among the youngsters to the highest stage. With aggressive agricultural practice, roads networks construction, rural and urban renewal, establishment of community development associations (CDAs), provision of electric power transformers, tourism and formal launching of Omoluabi Garment Factory in September 2013 which has capacity to engage 3000 workers signal a brighter future, job security and sustainable development, not only for the people but also the state in particular.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher used structured questionnaires and personal interview to obtain relevant data.

It is generally believed that the larger the sample size, the smaller the sampling error and also that a good sample is a good representation of the population from which it was drawn. Sample of 120 OYES corps in the population with equal and independent chances of being selected were randomly selected for this research.

Hypotethesis i.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between challenges and prospects of youth empowerment in the State development.

Hi: There is significant relationship between challenges and prospects of youth empowerment in the State development.

Hypotethis ii.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between youth empowerment and the State development.

Hi: There is significant relationship between youth empowerment and the State development.

Data Presentation, Analysis and interpretation

The researcher prepared and distributed 120 structured questionnaires among the cadets in three Local Government Areas (LGAs). The OYES cadet members were randomly selected based on their availability.

A total of 105 filled questionnaires were recovered from the respondents in three local government areas as follows: Olorunda 36, Ede North 35, and Egbedore 34 respectively but only 105 copies were recovered. The questionnaires served as the basis for data analysis.

Table 1: Youth empowerment reduced unemployment in the State of Osun.

ALTERNATIVE	RESPONDENT EDE NORTH LG	RESPONDENT OLORUNDA LG	RESPONDENT EGBEDORE LG	PERCENT
STRONGLY AGREE	17	16	13	43%
AGREE	12	14	15	39%
DISAGREE	3	2	2	7%
INDIFFERENT	3	4	4	11%
TOTAL	35	36	34	100%

Sources: Field survey, 2013.

From the table 1 above, it could be seen that 43% of the respondents strongly agreed, 39% agreed, 7% disagreed, while 11% were indifferent that there are challenges facing the implementation of OYES in the State of Osun. 35 respondents in Ede North, 36 in Olorunda, 34 in Egbedore local government areas respectively responded to the questionnaires administered.

Table 2: Youth employment scheme facilitates development in the State of Osun.

ALTERNATIVE	RESPONDENT EDE NORTH LG	RESPONDENT OLORUNDA LG	RESPONDENT EGBEDORE LG	PERCENT
STRONGLY AGREE	15	13	12	39%
AGREE	13	16	17	43%
DISAGREE	4	5	2	10%
INDIFFERENT	3	2	3	8%
TOTAL	35	36	34	100%

Sources: Field survey, 2013.

Table 2 above showed that 39% respondent representing various local government areas strongly agreed; 43% agreed. Summarily 82 percent of the cadets agreed that peoples-oriented programmes especially OYES scheme facilitated development in the State of Osun. However 10% of the respondents disagreed while 8% were indifferent to the question.

Testing of Hypothesis

For the reason that one hypothesis may be accepted or rejected does not indicate that as for this research study and OYES is concerned, they are only show to be correct and reasonable. Since the acceptance or rejection of hypothesis is based on the result of a sample taken from the respective population or a certain number of people, so at this junction the researcher needed to calculate the relationship between two (2) variables through correlation coefficient techniques in order to know and show how they are related.

- X--- Represent responses
- Y--- Represent percentages
- N--- Represent number or the respondents

Hypothesis II

This hypothesis was designed for the cadet members to know whether youths empowerments facilitate development of State of Osun.

Table 3 was designed to test this hypothesis correlation coefficient for hypothesis

N	X	Y %	XY	X ²	Y ²
Strongly agree	40	39	1560	1600	1521
Agree	46	43	1978	2116	1849
Disagree	11	10	110	121	100
Indifferent	8	8	64	64	64
$\Sigma N=4$	$\Sigma 105$	$\Sigma 100$	$\Sigma 3712$	$\Sigma 3901$	$\Sigma 3534$

$$\begin{aligned}
 RX-1 &= \frac{N \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} \sqrt{N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2}} \\
 &= \frac{4(3712) - (105)(100)}{\sqrt{4(3901) - (105)^2} \sqrt{4(3534) - (100)^2}} \\
 &= \frac{14848 - 10500}{\sqrt{(15604 - 11025)(14136 - 10000)}} \\
 &= \frac{4348}{\sqrt{4579 \times 4136}} \\
 &= \frac{4348}{\sqrt{18938744}} \\
 &= \frac{4348}{4351.87} = 0.9991
 \end{aligned}$$

Interpretation: There is positive strong correlation and it shows that youth empowerment is significant to development in the State of Osun.

Summary of Findings

The findings revealed that the Osun Youth Empowerment Scheme (OYES) has succeeded in empowering the beneficiaries in terms of skill acquisition for self-employment. Although the programme is still ongoing, there are still more to be expected. OYES in all ramifications is a successful project which has empowered 20,000 youths (Batch 1) that had hitherto lost all hopes of survival. OYES has contributed tremendously to fostering state development. Moreover, the scheme did intervene in the plight of the youths by providing them opportunities for acquisition of vocational/entrepreneurial skills of varied kinds which made them not only to be self-reliant but also empowered them to be more efficient in the discharge of their responsibilities to their individual family members, communities and Nigeria at large. The investigation revealed that the beneficiaries, more so among university and polytechnic graduates, were able to set up their own businesses such as O-tech, O-beaf, O-power (Bio-gas), O-Reap, O-meal and Green gang after graduating from the training schemes. There was an improved sense of commitment among the participants in OYES projects. This was evidenced by their prompt, enthusiastic response on experiences gathered during the training periods, the new change in their socio-economic status as a result of the skill acquired, and the fact that most of them were not only self-employed but also employers of labour. The then voluntary scheme turned to permanent self-sustained opportunity.

Conclusion

This study attempted capturing the role of youth empowerment scheme in the development of the State of Osun. The future belongs to the youths who make productive use of their knowledge, skills and character to positively affect the development of the state. This can only be through skill acquisition and positive

orientation seminars. From all indications, youth unemployment is a menace in Nigeria and constitutes a real danger and a threat to the state development of Osun. Against this background, there is the need by government at all levels and other stakeholders to embark on massive youth empowerment schemes for the envisaged development of the community around them and that of the nation. If a state requires developing socio-economically and politically it needed to advance natural and human resources availability in a multidimensional way.

The findings revealed that the Osun Youth Empowerment through its various trainings did re-orientate cadets' attitudes towards self and societal development; inculcate in trainees the appropriate entrepreneurial skills and attitudes for creativity, innovation and enterprise which enabled them tackled unemployment and contributed to the economic wellbeing of their communities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Excessive reliance on the government for the provision of every required socio-economic resources and the jobs creation has been the bane of development efforts in Nigeria. Government alone cannot provide all facilities due to her limited resources and population explosion. Government must as a matter of urgency place her priority right; create an enabling environment for the private sector/peoples' participation programmes in building the State to an enviable level.

There is a growing need for creativity in the modern society. The State Government of Osun should ensure continuity and improve on distribution of updated Tablet of Knowledge (Opon Imo) to public tertiary institutions and secondary schools students who as from year 2015 would write compute-base-test (CBT) examinations in West African Examinations Council and University and Tertiary Matriculation Examinations because education is the best pivotal legacy on which sustainable development rest.

Government should reach out to more youths, regardless of their ethnic, cultural, religious, educational background and geographical or political affiliation, and that the programme should be legislated so that new or succeeding government would not obstruct its continuity for sustainable development.

Zonal youth/leadership development centres should be established in the state/country for leadership/entrepreneurial/vocational training which would enable the youths and adults who are interested in manpower development effort of the State to promote sustainable self-empowerment to gainfully discover their potentials and cultivate a habit of excellence as unique brands, establish and manage their own businesses to take them out of crimes and become productive, self-reliant and development conscious.

Other States and the Federal Government should emulate State of Osun's hands-on approach to youth's empowerment and peoples' programmes to check the rate of unemployment and fast-track national development.

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APPENDIX

OYESsegmentation and deployment

s/n	Local Government Office	Nominal Roll Strength	Percent age Strength	Green Gang 3000		Sanitation Czars 3000	Sheriff Guard	Traffic mgrs	Teachers Corps 5000	Public Work 4000	Paramedics 2000	Task force 1000	Total	
				Watt	Other								Gr and	Wei gth
0	2	3	4	5		6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
1	BOLUWADURO	488	2.6	39	39	77	20	31	128	103	51		488	173
2	BORIPE	640	3.4	48	54	101	20	47	168	135	67		640	230
3	IFEDAYO	818	4.3	57	72	129	20	66	215	172	86		818	295
4	IFELODUN	761	4.0	15	105	120	20	60	200	160	80		761	235
5	ILA	609	3.2	49	48	96	20	44	180	128	64		609	220
6	IREPODUN	650	3.4	40	51	180	20	48	171	72	68		650	160
7	ODO-OTIN	600	3.2	48	47	95	20	43	158	126	63		600	217
8	OLORUNDA	1099	5.8	60	87	200	138	79	289	131	116		1099	270
9	OROLU	686	3.6	54	108	254	20	31	181	44	72		686	129
10	OSOGBO	1260	6.6	50	147	199	200	50	332	150	133		1260	250
11	ATAKUMOSA EAST	363	1.9	29	28	57	20	18	96	76	38		363	123
12	ATAKUMOSA WEST	488	2.6	39	38	77	20	31	128	103	51		488	173
13	IFE CENTRAL	663	3.5	53	52	105	20	50	174	140	70		663	243
14	IFE EAST	343	1.8	27	27	54	20	16	90	72	36		343	115
15	IFE NORTH	495	2.6	39	39	78	20	32	130	104	52		495	175
16	IFE SOUTH	391	2.1	31	31	62	20	21	103	82	41		391	134
17	AREA OFFICE	382	2.0	15	30	129	20	15	101	31	40		382	61
18	ILASA EAST	551	2.9	44	43	87	20	38	145	116	58		551	198
19	OBOKUN	626	3.3	50	49	99	20	46	165	132	66		626	228
20	ORIADE	453	2.4	36	36	72	24	28	119	95	48		453	159

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21	ILASA WEST	610	3.3	49	49	98	20	45	163	130	65	619	224
22	AYEDA ADE	658	3.5	52	52	104	20	49	173	139	69	658	240
23	AYEDIRE	445	2.3	35	35	70	20	27	117	94	47	445	156
24	EDE NORTH	692	3.6	55	54	173	20	53	182	82	73	692	150
25	EDE SOUTH	596	3.1	47	47	174	20	43	157	45	63	596	135
26	EGBEDORE	656	3.5	52	52	149	20	49	173	93	69	656	154
27	EJIGBO	521	2.7	41	41	82	20	35	137	110	55	521	136
28	IREWOLE	726	3.8	58	57	115	20	56	191	153	76	726	227
29	ISOKAN	478	2.5	38	37	75	20	30	126	101	50	478	169
30	IWO	790	4.2	63	62	125	20	63	208	166	83	790	292
31	OLA-OLUWA	435	2.4	36	36	72	20	28	119	95	48	453	159
	TOTAL	19000	100	1345	1653	3508	918	1221	5000	3350	2000	20000	6000

OYES volunteers were massively deployed into the streets for their respective duties, the teachers Corp was later added in response to a desperate emergency.

DEPLOYMENT AREAS OF OYES IN THE STATE OF OSUN

(Culled from OYES First Anniversary Programme. Saturday 5th May, 2012)

